

E-VOLVE EV FOR LIFE, VALUE, EFFICIENCY

NEWSLETTER 01/25

Holiday season is over and we all used our holiday breaks to gain energy for the upcoming year. With all that new motivation we started into 2025 and are very proud of our next newsletter edition which we herewith would like to present to you.

We have a new cluster member we are introducing to you in this issue and some exciting project news. In addition, we attended some conferences and events we would like to tell you about. Lastly, as mentioned in the last newsletter edition, the cluster held another webinar in November of last year. Be sure to check out the article about it to find out what was going on and where you can find the videos to rewatch it.

Enjoy this issue and be sure, we have a lot in store for this year; so don't miss the newsletters that will follow!

WELCOME NEW MEMBERS

CliMAFlux

CIRCULAR DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUES FOR NEXT-GENERATION HIGHLY-EFFICIENT INTEGRATED AXIAL FLUX MOTOR DRIVES FOR ELECTRIC VEHICLES

Electric traction machines are at the heart of the transition towards a zero tailpipe emission road mobility landscape, with their performance and cost directly impacting the attainable market penetration of electric vehicles. To accelerate the transition, next-generation electric motors need to push the existing boundaries in terms of efficiency, power density, manufacturability, cost, and environmental sustainability. A reduced and more circular use of rare earth resources is critical to reinforce Europe's strategic autonomy and establish a more economically sustainable value chain. Recently developed axial flux motor technology based on a yokeless and segmented armature topology yields promising prospects in

all these areas, significantly reducing the required amount of rare earth magnet material by design, and combining this with unmatched power density compared to state-of-the-art radial flux machines.

CliMAFlux will develop novel concepts (e.g. in terms of excitation and cooling) for more performant (e.g. >35% energy loss decrease in driving cycles) axial flux motors, thus reducing the need for rare earth materials by 60%, leveraging high-fidelity multiphysics models (e.g. electromagnetic, thermal, mechanical, and at the system level) and digital twins. Innovative designs and manufacturing processes will be proposed to: (i) increase the power density to >23 kW/l, through novel materials and improved thermal behaviour; (ii) enhance circularity over the lifetime (including >70% recyclability at the end of life); and (iii) ensure cost competitiveness (50% cost reduction) at mass production level (reaching ~€5/kW). The CliMAFlux on-board motors are integrated with the power electronics and mechanical transmission systems. The resulting electric drives will be managed by robust predictive controllers based on the CliMAFlux digital twins, including artificial intelligence (AI) prediction models, which will also facilitate novel functionalities in vehicle (sub)systems, hereby

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exploiting the full capability of the complete electrified drivetrain. The individual motor (with focus on approx. 90 kW continuous power) and integrated drive system will be benchmarked over a wider range of vehicles, in terms of both performance and environmental impact, on virtual (X-in-the-Loop with digital twin) and hardware test platforms up to TRL7, i.e. on a research electric vehicle already available at the consortium participants.

To achieve these ambitious targets, ClIMAFlux brings together the competences of 4 academic

partners, 1 industry-oriented RTO, 3 SMEs and 1 LE with dedicated R&D and production facilities in the fields of motor and transmission development, power electronics integration, electrified vehicle systems, automotive design, and life cycle assessment and costing aspects.

In summary, ClIMAFlux will establish new knowledge and industrial leadership in key digital, enabling and emerging technologies, and, therefore, directly contribute to Europe's Key Strategic Orientations C and A as well as actively support the transformation towards zero tailpipe emission road mobility (2Zero).

ClIMAFlux is coordinated by the University of Ghent and the consortium consists of 9 partners from five different countries.

Follow the project:

PROJECT NEWS

New Paper: E-gear functionality based on mechanical relays in permanent magnet synchronous machines

Permanent magnet synchronous machines (PMSMs) are still the first choice for use in electric vehicles due to their unparalleled efficiency and power density. However, they suffer from an inherently limited speed range. As field weakening or the addition of a mechanical gearbox deteriorates the efficiency of the drive, it is suggested in this paper to equip the drive with

reconfiguration switches, giving rise to a so-called e-gear. The switches—which are implemented by means of mechanical relays—allow to change the winding connection of the electric machine from a series to a parallel connection and hence to double its efficient speed range. Simulations and experimental results on a 4-kW axial-flux PMSM confirm the feasibility of the concept and prove that the reconfiguration can be conducted in less than 35 ms.

Read the full paper by [Hendrik Vansompel](#), et al. [HERE](#).

Follow the project:

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PAST CONFERENCES & EVENTS

ToSVE

Back in November of 2024, the Politecnico di Torino (PoliTO) organised the ToSVE event for the second time. First, this article will introduce what was going on at the event and exhibition. Then, we will share which cluster projects contributed to the poster session. Last, we have two partners from the projects talking about their experience at the event.

ToSVE 2nd Edition (2024) – Towards the Sustainable Vehicle Era: A meeting point where research, businesses, and young talent converge. The event was held on November 8th and attracted over 250 participants and more than 100 businesses, elevating it beyond traditional career fairs and scientific conferences. It was a bold initiative to foster collaboration and drive innovation in vehicles and sustainable mobility. Businesses showcased their activities, while the Polytechnic researchers presented cutting-edge topics that captured the interest of the industry. Organized by the interdepartmental CARS and PEIC centers, this event highlighted PoliTO's commitment to comprehensive research that addresses the entire supply chain related to terrestrial mobility, emphasizing the importance of collaboration between academia and industry.

At ToSVE, professors, researchers, automotive industry leaders, and students came together to engage in meaningful discussions about emerging trends, transformative projects, and

opportunities for sustainable mobility—both now and in the future. The agenda included focused sessions on three pivotal themes: **Trends in Sustainable Vehicles, Autonomous and Connected Vehicles, and Emerging Technologies and Components.**

Figure 1: Impressions from the exhibition

These sessions ensured that participants gained a comprehensive understanding of the advancements shaping the future of sustainable mobility. Additionally, an exhibition showcased prototypes and posters, facilitating an active exchange of ideas and innovations. Attendees also enjoyed guided visits to the CARS and PEICS labs.

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Figure 2: Presentations at the ToSVE event

PoliTO effectively addresses a wide range of technological knowledge, combining both academic insights and practical experiences of collaborating with companies to develop new products. This focus is especially important because most Italian companies are medium-sized or small and often lack the resources to conduct independent research. Additionally, the Polytechnic strongly emphasizes the application of new technologies in industrial contexts. As a result, many speakers at the event were representatives from various companies rather than PoliTO researchers.

Figure 3: Impressions of the poster presentation

These representatives shared their experiences of working with researchers, providing companies with concrete examples of the opportunities that can arise from collaborating with one of Europe's leading research institutions. In contrast, the space allocated for PoliTO researchers mainly featured a poster session and a display of prototypes developed in partnership with

companies that already partner with the University.

This event demonstrates a strong commitment to conducting applied research alongside companies, a principle that PoliTO aims to cultivate and expand by allowing companies to share their experiences with the academic world.

Find out more about the event and [watch the video recap](#).

We are very proud that three of our cluster projects contributed to the poster session: [EM-TECH](#), [HighScope](#) and [SmartCorners](#).

Not only was this a perfect opportunity for the project partners to have an informal meeting, but also to chat with colleagues from other EU projects and companies working on similar topics.

Here are further impressions from the poster session of the event:

Figure 4: [Irving Aguilar Zamorate](#) and [Antonella Accardo](#) both from PoliTO in front of the EM-TECH project poster

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Figure 5: [Nicola Amati](#) (PoliTO) and the HighScope poster

These sessions are always a great way to stay in contact with other projects and stay up-to-date on the latest research activities.

Figure 6: [Aldo Sorniotti](#) (PoliTO), [Eric Armengaud](#) (Armengaud Innovate GmbH) and [Nicola Amati](#) (PoliTO) in front of the project poster for SmartCorners

On behalf of all partner projects and partners that participated, we would like to thank PoliTO for the organisation of this very interesting event and the opportunity to present the projects at the poster session.

Here are a few words from the project partners presenting their activities:

[Elaphe](#) – Propulsion Technologies:

“Elaphe is proud to have participated in the *“Towards the Sustainable Vehicle Era 2024”* event with our prototype *Hyundai Ioniq 5* back in November 2024, showcasing the incredible potential of our software-defined in-wheel technology.

A highlight of the event? Elaphe's **patent-pending vibroacoustic feature**, which generates sound directly from the in-wheel motors, delivering a unique and immersive driving experience.

A big thanks to [Tomaž Kompara](#), [Jurij Kern](#), and [Iztok Franko](#) for representing Elaphe and demonstrating how our technology is shaping the future of sustainable mobility.”

Figure 7: [Jurij Kern](#) and [Tomaž Kompara](#) at their stand for Elaphe

[Claudio Romano](#) from Ideas & Motion:

“*Ideas & Motion* focuses on technical excellence and innovation in developing high-efficiency power inverters for the electric mobility sector. Its clear objectives include research and development, transforming innovation into products and accessing best-in-class technologies.

The business operates along two key lines:

- Delivering engineering services in both hardware (HW) and software (SW) domains for the automotive industry.

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- *Supplying smart control systems for niche applications characterized by low volumes and high technological content in the e-mobility and telemetry module sectors.*

I&M was honored to be able to present an overview of SiC-based power electronics solutions developed in different R&D activities at the event and would like to thank PoliTO for the opportunity.”

Figure 8: Insights from Ideas & Motion

Once again we would like to thank PoliTO for the organisation of this event and are very much looking forward to the next edition of this get-together.

[Carla Galluzzi](#), Politecnico di Torino

[Anna Zamecnik](#), Armengaud Innovate GmbH

SEE MOBILITY E-VOLV(E)ING

The E-VOLVE Cluster webinar

Smart Components for the Software-Defined Vehicle of the Future

That was the motto underlying the cluster webinar last November. This webinar was the second issue of this year and gave cluster projects the opportunity to present their take on the topic.

As the automotive industry shifts towards increased digitalization, smart components are playing a key role in shaping the next generation of vehicles. The Software Defined Vehicle represents a transformative approach.

Software innovation is key to increase vehicle performance, enable autonomous driving, and offer new services to users. This webinar presented 7 projects, all members to the E-VOLVE Cluster that are paving the way for this technological shift. Each project showcased how their innovative components contribute to the SDV concept of the future, presenting their latest results, innovations, and future outlook.

The following presentations were part of the webinar:

- [SCAPE](#): “Prognosis and health-management strategies for the EV powertrain” by Dr. Àlber Filbà, IREC
- [PowerDrive](#): “The Road towards Efficient and Compact Onboard Chargers” by Hans Wouters, KU Leuven
- [HiPE](#): “Active suspension system” by Dr. Bernhard Brandstätter, Virtual Vehicle
- [HighScope](#): “Power-electronics as innovation driver for smart components” by Dr. Sebastian Gramstat, AUDI

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- [EM-TECH](#): “Fast-reaction in-wheel motors driving towards new vehicle control strategies” by DI Martin Weinzerl, AVL List GmbH
- [SmartCorners](#): “Smart Corner solution for disruptive and user centric mobility” by Dr. Aldo Sorniotti, PoliTO
- [EFFEREST](#): “Smart cabin climatization concepts through comfort based HVAC control” by Sebastian Möller, Virtual Vehicle.

More than 80 interested participants representing various stakeholders attended the event and we are delighted to have received wonderful feedback.

This event proved once again, that we can create a substantial impact when working together. The partner projects presented some very interesting insights into their research and offered some room for a fruitful discussion. We want to thank everyone for their presentation, participation and organisation of this event and are very much looking forward to the next E-VOLVE cluster webinar!

If you want to find out more about the webinar and presentations that were held, go to the [E-VOLVE Cluster website](#) and rewatch them.

[Ingrid Armenqaud](#) and [Anna Zamecnik](#), Armengaud Innovate GmbH – [EM-TECH](#) / [HighScope](#)

UPCOMING EVENTS

RTR CONFERENCE 2025

From February 11th to 13th it is once again time for the RTR Conference in Brussels. This conference is a very important event for the automotive sector to discuss and exchange on the results from road transport research.

Therefore, we are very honored that many of cluster projects were invited to be a part of this event. Here is a summary of the agenda. We strongly recommend to attend the presentations of our member projects:

February 12th 2025 – 9:00-11:15

“Innovative components for more efficient EVs” – presentation of the projects EM-TECH, MAXIMA, HEFT, VOLTCAR and CliMAFlux

February 12th 2025 – 11:45-13:00

“Innovative components for more efficient EVs” – presentation by SCAPE

Be sure to come and visit the presentations or join online. [Register here](#)

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COMING UP

EM-TECH

General Assembly

February 5th – 6th 2025

Next E-VOLVE Cluster Meeting

February 7th 2025

[RTR Conference 2025](#)

February 11th – 13th, 2025

EARPA Spring Meeting 2025
Brussels

March 4th – 5th, 2025

SAE World Congress

April 8th – 10th 2025

Next edition of the E-VOLVE Newsletter

April 2025

Funded by
the European Union

The research leading to these results have received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme H2020 and Horizon Europe. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the funding authority. Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

